

Other Neuropteroids including Protorthoptera, Megaloptera and Raphidioptera

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Strephocladidae *Spargoptilon confertus* Carboniferous

HW

MEGALOPTERA: Corydalidae

HW:MEGALOPTERA: Corydalidae

Corydalidae: Archichauliodes sp.

Australia

Corydalidae: *Chauloides* sp. Quebec

HW: Megaloptera: Corydalidae: *Corydalid* sp.

HW Megaloptera: Corydalidae

Corydalidae: *Neohermes californicus*

FW Corydalidae: *Neohermes californicus*

In HW, ScP runs near base under R&MA

FW Corydalidae: *Neoneuromus latratus tonkiensis* India, Nakhu

Note that arculus occurs in many blattoids, all hemipteroids and all endopterygotes

HW Corydalidae: *Neoneuromus latratus tonkinensis*

Corydalidae: *Neurhermes* sp.

Corydalidae: *Nigronia* sp.

Quebec

FW Corydalidae: *Protochauliodes infuscatus*

Megaloptera: Corydalidae: *Protochauloides* sp.

HW Corydalidae: *Protochauliodes* sp.

3Ax folds when wings flex back. PR-PC&C not reduced

FW Megaloptera: Corydalidae: *Protohermes* sp. India

Protohermes
det M.T. Glorioso
cwc specimen
India (Kameng)
Rupa
11. 01. 1961
F. Schmid

Corydalidae: *Protohermes* sp.

Sialoptera: Sialidae: *Austrosialis* sp.

Sialidae: *Austrosialis* sp.

Sinusoid medial brace (ma-mp) present in HW

Sialoptera: Sialidae: *Sialis sibirica*

FW Dorsal View

FW VENTRAL VIEW

Sialid venation is close to Raphidioptera, NOT to Megaloptera (see "arcus=fusion" important for base reinforcement)

FW Sialoptera: Sialidae: *Sialis* sp.

Anal axillare (AX-A) long and subdivided
 FW: note fusion of MP and CuA replacing the
 arculus strut and other veinal characters similar
 as in Raphidioptera.
 Differences: in Raphidioptera HW, AA 3+4
 fuses at length in CuP. In Sialidae HW,
 AA 3+4 and CuP are separated by claval line

Fulcalaria M, Cu, A
 reduced

Sialoptera: Sialidae: *Stenosialis* sp.

FW Sialoptera: *Sialidae*

Details of sialid character states near wing base

Anal axalare (AX-A) long and subdivided
 FW: note fusion of MP and CuA replacing the arculus strut and other venal characters similar as in Raphidioptera.
 Differences: in Raphidioptera HW, AA 3+4 fuses at length in CuP. In Sialidae HW, AA 3+4 and CuP are separated by claval line

Raphidiidae: *Agulla (glavia) admixa*

Victoria, BC, Canada

Note that in Endoneoptera HW, separation of AA from anal lobe is often much less. But in this HW AA 3+4 distinctly joins remigium as in blattoids

Raphidioptera: Inocelliidae: *Inocellia* (Negha) *inflata* (Hagen)

In FW arcus is expressed as fusion between MP and CuA, as also in Sialidae (wrongfully placed into Megaloptera)

Raphidioptera: Inocelliidae: *Inocellia* (Negha) *inflata* (Hagen)

FW

"Humeral plate" (F&B-PC&C) clearly shows composition from two sclerites. Medial vein shows composition of two originally independent sectors (MA and MP)

Raphidioptera: Inocelliidae: *Inocellia inflata*

Shows: "humeral plate" as composed of two sclerites, PC & C-F plus PC&C-B. Medial fulcalare (M-F) is membranized.

Raphidioptera: Raphidiidae

FORE WING

HIND WING

Raphidioptera: Raphidiidae

FORE WING

HIND WING

Raphidioptera: Raphidiidae
FORE WING

HIND WING

Raphidioptera: Raphidiidae: *Raphidia admixa*

FORE WING

HIND WING

Raphidioptera: *Raphidiidae*

Fore wing

Hind wing

Agulla admixa

Raphidioptera: *Raphidiidae*

Fore wing

Hind wing

Agulla admixa

Raphidioptera: Raphidiidae: *Agulla (glavia) admixa* Victoria, BC, Canada

